

Hemisection: A Minimally Invasive Strategy to Rescue a Mandibular Molar

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Abstract

Hemisection serves as a conservative and multidisciplinary surgical endodontic prosthodontic intervention aimed at retaining salvageable portions of multi rooted teeth compromised by localized disease. In this case, a mandibular first molar with an endo-periodontal lesion underwent hemisection successfully. Following endodontic therapy and surgical excision of the diseased root, prosthetic rehabilitation with a fixed bridge restored form and function. The favorable outcome highlights hemisection as an effective alternative to extraction in selected cases.

Keywords: Hemisection , Mandibular Molar , Endo-Periodontal Lesion ,Prosthetic Rehabilitation, Surgical Excision.

Introduction

Modern conservative dentistry prioritizes the preservation of natural dentition over extraction and artificial replacement. This paradigm shift is based on an understanding of the biological and functional advantages of retaining the natural tooth structure, periodontal ligament, and alveolar bone. In this context, hemisection, or root amputation, emerges as a valuable treatment option for multi-rooted teeth, especially mandibular molars, where one root is non-restorable due to caries, vertical fracture, or advanced localized periodontal disease, while the other remains healthy and structurally sound.

Hemisection refers to the surgical separation and removal of one root and the associated coronal structure of a multirooted tooth, with the intent to preserve the remaining portion. The procedure allows the salvaging of a partially diseased tooth and provides a prosthetic foundation for long-term function and aesthetics. It is a multidisciplinary treatment, integrating principles of endodontics, periodontics, prosthodontics, and oral surgery, and demands careful planning and execution for successful outcomes^[1,2].

Indications for hemisection include irreparable root fractures, localized vertical bone loss affecting one root, failing endodontic treatment of one canal and root caries.^[3,4] The retained root must exhibit sufficient bone support, favourable anatomy, and the ability to withstand occlusal loading. The patient's oral hygiene, motivation, and medical status

also play a pivotal role in long-term success^[5].

Compared to extraction and implant placement, hemisection offers several advantages. It is biologically conservative, preserving the alveolar bone, soft tissues, and proprioceptive feedback mechanisms associated with the periodontal ligament. It is also economically favourable, avoiding the cost and surgical morbidity associated with implant therapy or bridge fabrication. Additionally, it maintains arch integrity, particularly important in younger patients or those contraindicated for implants^[6,7].

Despite these advantages, hemisection is underutilized in clinical practice. A probable cause is the increasing reliance on implants and a general perception that resective procedures are technique-sensitive and less predictable. However, recent literature has shown encouraging results with hemisection when strict selection criteria are followed. In a 10-year follow-up study, Bühler (1988) observed that root-resected molars had satisfactory long-term survival, especially when periodontal and prosthetic principles were adhered to^[8]. Fugazzotto (2001) similarly reported that resected molars, when properly restored, showed outcomes comparable to those of single implants^[9].

Technological advancements have further

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improved the predictability of hemisection. CBCT imaging provides detailed assessment of root morphology, furcation anatomy, and bone support, enabling precise case selection and surgical planning. Microsurgical techniques, improved rotary instrumentation, and bio-ceramic sealing materials have significantly enhanced the endodontic phase, while modern flap designs and magnification improve surgical precision^[10].

Nevertheless, hemisection requires a thorough understanding of occlusal dynamics, root morphology, and restorative planning. The prosthesis must be designed to evenly distribute occlusal forces, ensure accessibility for oral hygiene, and avoid overloading the retained root. Complications such as root fracture, periodontal breakdown, or caries in the remaining root can occur in poorly planned or maintained cases^[11,12].

In the era of evidence-based, patient-centered care, hemisection should be regarded as a viable, strategic alternative rather than a compromised solution. It aligns well with modern goals of minimally invasive dentistry, cost-effectiveness, and long-term function. With proper execution and patient compliance, hemisection remains a valuable tool in the clinician's armamentarium for managing complex molar cases conservatively.

Case Report

A 59-year-old male presented with intermittent pain and mobility in the lower-left molar region. Clinical Examination revealed that tooth #36 was non-vital with Grade I mobility and deep pockets (8–10mm) on the mesial/buccal aspects. Radiographic examination showed that a significant Grade II furcation defect, periapical radiolucency seen at the root apex. Vertical bone loss and root resorption present on distal aspect of mesial root. Distal root has adequate bone support.(fig.1,2

Diagnosis: On the basis of clinical and radiographic examination, Non vital tooth with periodontal lesion and bone defect present on the mesial root of #36.

Treatment Plan: Endodontic therapy followed by Hemisection (mesial root/crown removal) and PFM fixed partial denture from #35 to distal half of #36.

Fig-1 showing Preoperative clinical view

Fig-2. Preoperative Radiograph of #36

A- Working Length

B- Master Cone

C- Post Obturation

D- Post Endo Restoration
Fig-3

Procedure

Conventional root canal was done in distal root #36.(fig.3) After completion, the full thickness mucoperiosteal flap was raised and sectioning of the tooth through exposed furcation area by long sank tapered bur was done.(fig.5) Mesial root along with its crown portion was removed.(fig.6,7)

Fig-4 Armamentarium for Hemisection

Fig- 5 Vertical cut i.r.t. 36

Fig- 6 & 7. showing Extracted mesial segment of # 36

Thorough debridement of extracted soaked was done (fig.8) and odontoplasty of the remaining distal root was done and site was sutured with 3-0 silk suture material (fig.9) After completion of procedure ,Post operative radiograph was taken.(fig10)

Fig- 8 Removal of granulation tissue

Fig- 9. Suture placed

Outcomes: After One-week, patient was asymptomatic and no pain and swelling were present, sutures was removed.(fig.12)

At one-month follow-up, surgical site healed well.

Tooth preparation of #35 and #36 was done and impression were taken.(Fig.14)

Fabrication of prosthesis were done by dental laboratory ,cementation of prosthesis were done on patient mouth.(Fig.16)

Oral hygiene maintenance instructions was given to patient.

Fig- 10. Post operative radiograph

Fig- 12. Follow up after 1 week (Clinical view)

Fig- 13. 1 Month follow up radiograph

Fig- 14. Tooth preparation i.r.t. 35 & retained 36

Fig- 15. Prepared prosthesis

Fig- 16. Cementation of prosthesis in 35 & 36

Discussion

Hemisection, also referred to as root amputation or root resection depending on the clinical context, is a valuable and often underutilized treatment modality that enables the retention of part of a multi-rooted molar by removing the diseased or non-restorable root. This technique provides a conservative approach in situations where localized pathology affects a single root, such as advanced decay, vertical root fracture, or isolated periodontal destruction, while the remaining root remains healthy and structurally viable. The retained root, when properly treated, can continue to support occlusion and function effectively over the long term.

This method aligns with modern principles of conservative dentistry by preserving natural tooth structure and supporting tissues, avoiding more invasive and costly alternatives like extraction followed by implant therapy or prosthetic replacement. The biologic advantages of preserving the natural tooth include maintaining proprioception, preserving alveolar bone, and minimizing changes to occlusal dynamics.¹³

Case Selection: The Cornerstone of Success The prognosis of hemisection is highly dependent on careful case selection. Clinically, the most ideal cases involve mandibular molars with well-separated roots, favourable crown-to-root ratio, and limited bone loss surrounding the retained root. In contrast, maxillary molars often present greater challenges due to complex root anatomy, proximity of furcation, and difficulty in achieving an ideal emergence profile during prosthodontic rehabilitation.

Weine (1996) emphasized that a comprehensive assessment of root morphology, occlusal forces, periodontal status, and restorative possibilities is vital before proceeding. Cases with curved, fused, or short roots are generally contraindicated. Adequate interradicular bone support and accessibility for oral hygiene are essential for long-term success.¹⁴

Multidisciplinary Treatment Approach

Successful hemisection requires integration across multiple dental specialties:

Endodontic Phase: The retained root must undergo proper biomechanical preparation and obturation. Failure to create a hermetic seal may result in reinfection and treatment failure.

Surgical Phase: This includes flap design, precise root sectioning, and thorough debridement of granulation tissue. The resected surface should be contoured and smoothed to reduce plaque retention (DeSanctis and Murphy, 2000).¹⁵

Prosthodontic Phase: A full-coverage crown, often splinted to adjacent teeth, can protect the remaining structure and distribute occlusal forces. Proper emergence profile and hygiene access must be ensured.

Hemisection vs Implants and Extraction

Although dental implants have become the mainstream option for tooth replacement, hemisection offers several comparative advantages:

Preservation of Periodontal Ligament (PDL): Vital for proprioception and adaptive occlusion.

Alveolar Bone Maintenance: Hemisection maintains physiological stimulation to the bone.

Cost-effectiveness: Especially important in developing nations or for elderly patients.

Reduced Treatment Time and Risk: Avoids complications like sinus perforation or implant failure.

Dannewitz et al. (2006) showed that molars treated via respective periodontal surgery had favourable long-term outcomes. McGuire and Nunn (1996) supported the notion that many teeth performed better than their predicted prognosis if given appropriate follow-up and care.¹⁶

Restorative and Biomechanical Considerations

With the advent of modern adhesive dentistry, hemisection teeth can now be restored using fibre-reinforced posts, CAD/CAM-fabricated crowns, and precision occlusal adjustment. Periodontal splinting can enhance the longevity of compromised but restorable roots.

However, the altered biomechanics of the remaining root may lead to increased risk of fracture or overloading, especially in patients with bruxism. Occlusal guard therapy and regular occlusal monitoring are recommended in such cases.

Maxillary vs Mandibular Molars

Hemisection is more commonly indicated for mandibular molars, where straight mesial and distal roots are accessible and prosthodontic ally favourable. In maxillary molars, complex root morphology especially in the mesiobuccally and distobuccal roots may compromise the prognosis. In selected cases, however, retention of the palatal root can still be successful if anatomical and restorative conditions allow.

Long-Term Prognosis and Maintenance

Bühler (1988) demonstrated that with proper hygiene and follow-up, root-resected molars remained functional over a 10-year period. Common complications include:^{17,18}

- Secondary caries
- Periodontal pocket recurrence
- Root fracture
- Occlusal trauma

Hamp et al. (1975) and Rosenberg & Cho (2011) emphasized the importance of tailored maintenance therapy and long-term planning. Patient education and motivation are critical components of treatment success.^{19,20}

Conclusion

Hemisection represents a conservative, biologically sound, and cost-effective alternative to full molar extraction and prosthetic replacement. When executed with precise planning, strict case selection, and long-term maintenance, it offers excellent functional outcomes while preserving the natural architecture of the dentition. As dental professionals increasingly seek sustainable and patient-centered solutions, hemisection deserves renewed attention and wider inclusion in clinical decision-making. With emerging digital tools, improved materials, and interdisciplinary support, hemisection is poised for a well-deserved resurgence in the future of restorative and periodontal therapy.

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